

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' ARTISTIC-PICTURE THINKING IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF PAINTING

Ibatova Nigora Istamovna

Independent researcher of Bukhara State University

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Abstract. *The article discusses the relevance of developing students' artistic and visual thinking in the process of teaching painting, development of models for developing artistic and visual thinking of future teachers of fine arts in higher education institutions, teaching at all types and stages of education. The importance of increasing the efficiency of educational processes is explained.*

Keywords: *drawing science, artistic-image thinking, thinking model, efficiency, quality of education, life skills, professional competence.*

The current level of world development is characterized by the intellectualization of society. and on their basis the sustainability of development dynamics is ensured.

To increase the quality of education, to apply innovations and digital technologies to the educational process, in this process, the future visual arts teacher will be required not only to work with modern educational technologies, "Simple abilities" - information search and information holistic perception, positive and critical assessment of the content of information, teamwork, and creative, logical thinking, descriptive, artistic-figurative thinking are required. Therefore, it is urgent to improve the methodology of developing students' artistic thinking.

Development of models for the development of artistic thinking of future teachers of fine arts in the world's leading scientific centers and higher educational institutions, increasing the effectiveness of educational processes at all types and stages of education, education from school age scientific researches are being carried out on directing the recipient to the right profession, improving the artistic and creative competencies of students of higher education institutions through various forms of education.

In this process, on the basis of the "STEAM - education" program, the development of innovative teaching technologies for the development of the artistic and creative competence of students, the scientific worldview, the development of the artistic and visual thinking of future visual arts teachers, higher education issues of further improvement of the system of teaching subjects in the field of fine arts at the lim institution on the basis of competence approaches are gaining importance.

At the same time, it is necessary to develop the artistic and visual thinking of students in the teaching of drawing science through the combination of practical activities based on theoretical knowledge in the training of competitive personnel in accordance with the requirements of society.

Thinking is a high form of human mental activity and is a process of reflection of objective reality in the mind. Thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social phenomena, reality, and also the main condition for human activity. It is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more fully and accurately than intuition, perception, and imagination.

It is said to think, to reflect the things and events in reality by thinking, summarizing and mediating the connections between them. Reality is reflected in thinking, perception and imagination relatively deeper and more. We can learn things or events, properties of things or events, their connections and relationships through thinking, which we cannot know with the means of intuition and perception.

In the process of thinking, thoughts, opinions, ideas, assumptions, etc. are formed in a person's mind, and they are expressed in the form of concepts, judgments, conclusions. Thinking determines the reality of things and events that it reflects, perceives, and imagines in the activity of thinking, determines whether the formed judgments, concepts, conclusions are true or not. Through human thinking, it summarizes and directly (indirectly) reflects reality, understands the most important connections, relationships, and characteristics between things and events.

Thinking is the object of research in many fields of science. In the science of pencil drawing, thinking is divided into several types according to the level of generalization of reality, the nature of the problem-solving tool, the novelty of situations for a person, and the level of activity of a person.

They are researched separately: demonstrative action, demonstrative, practical, theoretical, voluntary, involuntary, abstract, creative, etc. Communication and relations between people in social life, educational process and production are also manifested with the help of thinking.

In the process of education, the qualities of thinking are formed, which include the acquisition of knowledge, the formation of competences in the field of science and the acquisition of skills necessary for life, a critical view, self-criticism, evaluation, inspection, self-examination, control, self-control, and group reasoning. The perception of a person by a person is also inextricably linked with thinking

Creative works, discoveries, inventions, proposals in the teaching of drawing are the products of thinking. Many complex problems of modern science require a deeper study of logical processes in thinking.

In our country, the system of preparing them for professional activity will be reformed by developing the artistic-figurative thinking of future art teachers in the teaching of "Penciling" subject.

In relation to this system, it is necessary to effectively use the possibilities of an international innovative and effective approach, to improve the scientific-based system of developing creative thinking in the preparation of state educational standards, qualification requirements, educational programs and integrated forms of education aimed at training high-level competent teachers. is increasing.

This, in turn, is the improvement of the methodology for the development of students' artistic and figurative thinking in the process of teaching the subject of "Pen and Drawing", which is taught in the field of visual arts of higher education, paying great attention to improving the quality of education, education design of content, development of new methodical models of teaching, the problem of the methodology of teaching visual arts requires deep study.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", PQ-4119 dated January 16, 2019 -No. "On additional measures to improve the quality control system of education" and the "Development strategy of New

Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026 "Glorification of human dignity" and the implementation of the "New Uzbekistan teachers" program, which was included in the State program for the implementation of the "year of active neighborhood" special emphasis was placed on the issues of further improvement of the quality of teaching art subjects, especially painting.

Based on the above ideas, after analyzing several scientific works, we set ourselves the task of carrying out a research work on the topic "Development of artistic and figurative thinking of students in the process of teaching the art of drawing".

The scientific-methodological basis of this research work is "the fourth direction of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 - fair social policy, development of human capital..."

While studying the research works on the topic, among the scientists of our country Sh.Kurbanov, N.A.Muslimov, B.B.Boymetov, R.K.Rajabov, S.F.Abdirasilov, K.M.Gulyamov, Sh.K.Mardonov, M.Abdullayeva, R.Hasanov, M.Kuronov, M.Vahobov, N.M.Egamberdiyeva, J.G'Yoldoshev, U.Tolipov, N.Sayidakhmedov, N.N.Azizkhodjayeva and others have researched the specific features of preparing future teachers for innovative activities. Kh.I.Ibragimov, U.I.Mahkamov, M.H.Usmonboyeva, J.E.Usarov, U.N.Khujamkulov, K.D.Riskulova, A.SH.Mukhsiyeva, O'.Toshmatov, Z.Ismoilova, Sh.Mustafayev, A.Muhamedov, H.Hamrayeva and others We have seen that they have implemented methodological and innovative approaches to the meaningful development of teachers' professional training.

S.S.Azimov, O.M.Jabborova, N.I.Yuldosheva, B.E.Khusanov and others, who conducted scientific research on this topic, developed the technology of developing artistic perception in future visual arts teachers, didactic teaching of developing artistic perception in future visual arts teachers It was found that they conducted research on the improvement of the teaching methodology of visual arts.

Chistyakov, D. Kardovsky, V. A. Slastenin, V. Anisimov, T. Dobrovolskaya, T. N. Komarova, V. M. Bekhterev, M. Sultanova, YE. Medvedeva, P. N. Nikonorova, A. Kuznetsova, I. Organizational and practical conditions of formation of visual thinking in preparation of future visual art teachers for innovative activities were studied by Levchenkos. In the research of foreign scholars G. Dore, Corrado Ricci, O. Dome, M. Albert, V. Greeny, W. John Morgan, Tony Bush, Lawrence A. Sherr, Deborah J. Teeter, future teachers of visual arts are innovative in the process of preparation for activities, researches were conducted on the theoretical and practical aspects of the formation of visual thinking.

Although a number of studies have been carried out on this problem, it is necessary to carry out scientific research on improving the methodology of developing students' artistic and figurative thinking in teaching the subject of "Painting and Drawing".

The main goal of our study of this topic is to develop suggestions and recommendations regarding the improvement of the methodology of developing students' artistic-figurative thinking in the teaching of the science of "pencil drawing", in which we put forward the following scientific hypotheses:

-If a methodical system for the development of students' artistic-image thinking is developed in the teaching of "pencil drawing";

-in this process, the psychological and didactic foundations of artistic thinking are relied upon;

if its methodical directions, the development of artistic thinking in future visual arts teachers, the mechanism and models of improving the methodology of teaching "Penciling" are developed and applied to educational practice;

In teaching the science of "pen drawing" there is an opportunity to get a guaranteed result in the system of developing students' artistic-image thinking.

In the course of this research, we determined the following tasks:

- clarification of the pedagogical conditions for the development of students' artistic-image thinking, improvement of methodological and didactic support in the process of teaching the science of "Painting" in the field of visual arts of higher education in pedagogic higher education institutions;

- improving the didactic model of developing the artistic thinking of future visual arts teachers;

-improving the methodology of developing students' artistic and visual thinking in the process of teaching "Pencil Drawing" in the training of future visual arts teachers;

- Development of methodical recommendations for improving the methodology of developing students' artistic and visual thinking in the process of teaching "pencil drawing".

In the course of our research, we plan to achieve the following scientific innovations:

- the content of methodological and didactic support for the development of the artistic and visual thinking of students in the teaching of the subject of "Painting and Drawing" in the field of visual arts of higher educational institutions of pedagogy, the pedagogical conditions such as graphic and creative stability of teaching visual arts is improved based on creative predictive refinement;

- Didactic model of development of students' artistic and visual thinking in the field of fine arts of higher educational institutions of pedagogy in the teaching of "Painting and Drawing" subject, types of work such as real and imaginative representation of composition modeling aimed at ensuring the integration of nature and education developed based on the introduction of field practice in an individual style demonstration environment.

-In the process of teaching the science of "pencil drawing", the methodology of developing the artistic and visual thinking of future teachers of fine arts, distinguishing the spectrum of colors, mobile applications that teach to aim in artistic creation, academic tour, personal gallery training-complex in the process is improved based on application in the environment of motivational orientation;

- the criteria for determining and evaluating the development levels of artistic and visual thinking in students are developed based on the transformation of qualities such as creativity, creativity, and artistry into competence levels of professional training in digital content.

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